

Research Article

Development of Smart Software Program for Production and Order Tracking in the Textile Industry

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(First received February 12, 2024 and in final form May 12, 2024)

Reference: Okyay, N., Kes, S., Işık, F., Uzun, A., T. Development of Smart Software Program for Production and Order Tracking in the Textile Industry. The European Journal of Research and Development, 4(2), 168-173.

Abstract

As a result of growth and development in the industry, difficulties in managing increasingly complex information flows, international competitive conditions, and rapid change in technology have led the business world to seek different solutions. At this point, computer-aided order tracking systems stand out as tools that provide advantages to businesses. In this way, it becomes possible to be successful in competition in an environment of constant change, to be able to predict changing business conditions and to respond quickly to them. Companies use ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) applications that ensure the efficient use of resources such as labor, machinery and materials required for the production of goods and services in their businesses. However, since these applications cover large areas, they cannot always provide a full solution to the specific operations of companies. Many business transactions in businesses are tracked through Excel tables. Within the scope of the study, it is aimed to develop an automation application that will allow companies to apply it without changing their operations, prevent errors and data loss with fixed formulas, and greatly increase efficiency with warning, order tracking and report structures.

Keywords: Yarn Business, Production and Order Tracking, MsSQL, HTML and CSS

1. Introduction

In the business world, quality, time and cost are of serious importance for the management of the business, and today the use of information technology has also been

added to these. In order for businesses to gain superiority over other businesses in the competitive environment, business planning and follow-up must be carried out quickly and systematically. Like all manufacturing sectors, orders received in yarn mills in the textile industry are determined before production starts, and then production dispatch planning is made. This planning is carried out by the planning department in businesses according to the demands of the customer or the corporate memory of the company. This planning document is distributed to the production-related departments of the enterprise in written forms by preparing a template on the Excel program, and this form is called a work order. This form contains the number, blend content, twist, cone type and deadline information of the yarn to be produced. In order for these prepared work order forms to be processed, the approval of authorized persons must be obtained and it requires a long process and follow-up. Additionally, after the work order is prepared, it may be necessary to make some changes depending on the customer or business situation, and this causes the process to take longer and errors to occur. In addition, the color of the cone on which the yarn will be wound is also of great importance and it is necessary to follow it in order to avoid mixing the types of yarn produced. When the literature studies on this subject are examined; studies have been found regarding determining the place and importance of the ERP system for ready-made clothing enterprises [1] and revealing the relationship between the ERP system and production activity control systems [2]. It has been concluded that production planning is made using computer-aided production tracking [3] and decision support systems [4] in the weaving, knitting and apparel activity areas of the textile industry. However, since there are not many material and product variables in spinning mills, Excel templates and basic software programs are used instead of large and comprehensive ERP systems. In this sense, a digital application needs to be developed to track yarn production and shipment in an error-free and efficient manner. Taking into account all these requirements, within the scope of the study, it is aimed to design a web application that enables data exchange over the network and tracking of order statuses and adapting it to businesses.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Within the scope of the study, a web application will be developed to create the work order format, including the type of raw material in the yarn composition, blend ratio, yarn number and twist, machine elements to be used in spinning that vary depending on the yarn type, cone color information, fixing status, customer and deadline information.

2.2. Methods

In the study, the database where the data will be stored, Front-End, where the data will be interpreted and processed and the user interface will be created and Back-End structures will be created to ensure database communication with the Front-End.

Microsoft Structured Query Language (MsSQL) technology will be used for the database, .NET CORE 5.0 WEB API technology, EntityFrameworkCore 5.0.8 auxiliary libraries, C# programming language, and Microsoft Visual Studio IDE will be used for the Back-End. For Front-End, Angular CLI 12.2.9 technology, Angular Material auxiliary libraries, Typescript, HTML and CSS programming languages, Visual Studio Code IDE will be used. In addition, in the program to be developed, the e-signature method will be used so that authorized persons can approve the created work order form. The web application to be developed will be created within the framework of clean code, object-oriented programming, modularity and divisibility, performance and optimization, security and reusability criteria.

3. Results

The production and order tracking software program to be developed within the scope of the study has a user interface that can be accessed by authorized persons and includes a Home Page where the latest status of the created work order forms is listed, a Plan Creation Page where the information in the work order form is filled in and the work order is created, a Production-Dispatch Transaction Page, where production-shipment information for each work order is included and updated, a Customer Transaction Page, where all customers the company works with are listed, a Cone Transaction Page, where all existing cones are listed and stock is tracked and a Production-Delivery Report Page, which contains a graphical report of all the yarns the company produces to its customers. The image of the software program developed within the scope of the study is given in Figure 1.

İş Yap	Durum	İş Emri No	Miktarı	İş Emri Tarihi	İplik Final	İplik İsmi	Harman Lotu	İplik Lotu	İplik Çeşidi	Konik Rengi	Sipariş Tarihi	T. Ba		
İşlem Yap	BEKLEMEDE	CAN TEKSTİL	20111638	600 KG	23-00444	6	6/1 CARDED SLUB WEA	-	KSD-246	PAMUK	4.20 EFLATUN HASIR	11.07.2023	20.07	
İşlem Yap	SIPARIŞ ALINDI	AYMES TEKSTİL	KRIC23-551	5000 KG	23-00443	11	11/1 CARDED SLUB WEA	-	KSD-245	PAMUK	4.20 KIRMIZI 46	11.07.2023	25.07	
İşlem Yap	URETİMDE	AR-GE	22007 PROJE	100 KG	23-00441	11.5	11.5/1 CAR NAİA WEA 60/40	-	-	KARIŞIM	4.20 TURUNCU DÜZ	05.07.2023	22.07	
İşlem Yap	BEKLEMEDE	SAVE TEKSTİL	23-00440	6	6/1 CAR REC COTTON SLUB KN	-	-	-	-	PAMUK	5.57 ZEMBE DÜZ	06.07.2023	11.07	
İşlem Yap	BEKLEMEDE	NESA TEKSTİL	23-00435	10	10/1 PUFFY TWIST COM CAR 4	-	-	-	-	PAMUK	5.57 ZEMBE YIL DİZ	01.06.2023	15.07	
İşlem Yap	BITTİ	CAN TEKSTİL	23-00434	8	8/1 CAR HEMP WEA 50/50	-	K20289	KHEMPO-140	-	DOĞAL	20 NATUREL DÜZ	14.06.2023	10.07	
İşlem Yap	BITTİ	ACN İPLİK	23-00433	3.84	3.84/1 COMBED TAIL TWIST	-	ITH469	TTP-80	-	PAMUK	5.57 SIYAH YILDIZ	09.01.2023	10.02	
İşlem Yap	BEKLEMEDE	NOM İPLİK	KRIC23-526	200 KG	23-00430	28	28/1 VISCON WEA	-	VD-34	SENTETİK	5.57 MAVİ KARELİ	06.07.2023	17.07	
İşlem Yap	BEKLEMEDE	SAVE TEKSTİL	KRIC23-524	4500 KG	23-00429	6	6/1 CARDED SLUB KNIT	-	YRL429	KST-157	PAMUK	4.20 PİEMBE 7	06.07.2023	11.07
İşlem Yap	BEKLEMEDE	CIRCULAR SYSTEM	27	200 KG	23-00428	7	7/1 ORG CAR ASRALOOP WEA 70/30	-	K20293	OKAGD-13	DOĞAL	4.20 KAHVERENGİ ZEBRA	05.04.2023	06.07

Figure 1: Image of the developed production and order tracking software program

In addition, the developed software program includes user restrictions, mandatory information entries, automatic calculation of information linked to each other with formulas, necessary filters and warning structures, and the images in which the program performs these filtering and warnings are given in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively.

Depoda toplam 151 adet konik çeşidi bulunmaktadır.

- 139 tanesi seçilebilir.
 - Bunlardan 120 tanesi hiçbir kurala takılmadığı için seçilebilir.
 - Bunlardan 19 tanesi en az bir kurala takıldığı halde farklı iplik çeşidinden dolayı seçilebilir.
- 12 tanesi seçilemez.
 - Bunlardan 1 tanesi şu an işletmede kullanıldığı için seçilemez.
 - Bunlardan 9 tanesi işletmede kullanılan koniklere benzerlikten dolayı seçilemez.
 - Bunlardan 7 tanesi 3 ay kuralından dolayı seçilemez.

Çapı	Rengi	Deseni	Adedi	Klişeli mi?
5.57	YEŞİL	DAMALI	602	KLIŞESİZ
5.57	TURUNCU	ZEBRA	3957	KLIŞESİZ
5.57	KIRMIZI	ZEBRA	4119	KLIŞESİZ
5.57	MAVİ	DAMALI	1310	KLIŞESİZ
5.57	YEŞİL	ZEBRA	4995	KLIŞESİZ
5.57	EFLATUN	ZEBRA	6289	KLIŞESİZ
5.57	YEŞİL	KARELİ	5317	KLIŞESİZ
4.20	KAHVERENGİ	DÜZ	4266	KLIŞESİZ
5.57	SARI	DÜZ	466	KLIŞESİZ
4.20	SIYAH	O	909	KLIŞESİZ

Figure 2: Cone filtering image of the developed production and order tracking software program

Figure 3: Insufficient cone quantity warning image of the developed production and order tracking software program

It has been concluded that the production and order tracking program developed within the scope of the study has positive effects and functionality such as ease of use because it does not consist of complex structures and sections, quick access to the desired information thanks to the filtering feature, timely delivery of orders to the customer with warning structures, reducing error rates with authorization processes and creating the corporate memory of the company by keeping work order history records, ensuring stability in production and thus meeting customer satisfaction.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Information technologies are systems that aim to examine and group information, deliver it to users in a certain order and make it available for use. The obligations of businesses to manage their resources in the best possible way, to ensure customer satisfaction, and to create a technological infrastructure for information management have led to the development of new applications within information technologies and their adaptation to business management [5]. Based on this, trying to carry out the production and order tracking within the company using the Excel application, which is the basic level, causes significant loss of time and business disruptions due to incorrect or incomplete information entries. Within the scope of the study, it was aimed to develop a software program to create a technological infrastructure and adapt it to the business in order to make production and order tracking practical, fast and error-free. It was concluded that the production and order tracking program developed within the scope of the study contributed to the prevention of time, production and financial losses while providing user convenience and systematic working comfort. Thanks to digital tracking, faulty productions are prevented, waste of raw materials and energy resources is prevented, and sustainable production is achieved. In addition, it has been observed that the developed production and order tracking program model provides information accuracy and reliability by allowing work orders to be created only by authorized persons,

elimination of risk factors by including warning structures, security by access restrictions, and traceability by being able to view the arrangements made.

5. Acknowledge

A contribution to the literature will be made by sharing this study, which was carried out at Karacasu Tekstil, on the platform of Nuh Naci Yazgan University. We would like to express our endless gratitude to our chairman of the board of directors, Mr. Mehmet Fethi Arifiođlu, our board members, Mr. Deniz Arifiođlu Akbař and Mr. Burak Orhan Arifiođlu, and to Nuh Naci Yazgan University, who provided us with all kinds of opportunities.

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